

PROBLEMS OF PROFESSIONAL CULTURE AND ORIENTATION IN STUDENTS AND THEIR PEDAGOGICAL CORRECTION

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Annotation: This article studies the problems of professional culture and orientation in students and their pedagogical correction, and recommendations are given.

Keywords: Professional culture, life plans, professional orientation, professional deformation.

One of the characteristics of students is the formation of life plans. On the one hand, life plans arise as a result of the generalization and consolidation of the goals set by the individual. On the other hand, the process of concretization of goals and motives occurs.

Life plans in students are simultaneously a social and moral phenomenon. The problems of who to be (professional identity awareness) and how to be (moral self-awareness) are considered to be fully formed during the student period. In some cases, some students have scattered life plans and do not correspond to their practical activities. They answer “yes” to the question “Do you have life plans?”, the specialty they are studying and need to master is still there, but the motivation to enter it, to become a deep owner of the chosen profession is very weak. A life plan is important not only in terms of the final result, but also in the methods and ways to achieve it, the objective and subjective opportunities necessary for it. That is why life plans come. Unlike active and imaginative students, a life plan is an activity plan, which primarily depends on the choice of a profession. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan also emphasizes that a person has the right to choose a profession in accordance with his abilities, qualifications and interests, along with the right to work.

Today, career orientation is a multidimensional and multilevel process that can be viewed from different perspectives. Firstly, as a series of tasks set by society for a developing individual, which must be solved sequentially by the individual over a certain period of time. Secondly, the individual is manifested as a decision-making process that forms his interests and abilities. Thirdly, as the process of forming any individual style, professional activity is manifested as a part of it. These three points of view are different aspects of work that complement each other. The main issue here is the state of professional orientation of students and the factors that oppose it.

The professional orientation of students is not only a social but also a pedagogical problem. In pedagogy, there are three points of view on professional orientation. The first point of view is based on the idea of the practical variability and stability of individual characteristics, which depend on the success and methods of activity. In this, on the one hand, the emphasis is on directing and selecting people suitable for this or that job to the profession, and on the other hand, on the selection of professions that are suitable for the individual characteristics of this or that person and strengthening adaptation to it. The second point of view is based on the idea of the purposeful formation of abilities, which involves the development of the important qualities of each person. Both of the above points of view can

be formulated differently, but their common methodological flaw is that individuality and labor activity are considered as unrelated, opposing, necessarily subordinate to each other magnitudes. The third point of view is based on the principle of the unity of consciousness and activity, and is aimed at the formation of an individual style of activity.

This concept is based on the following views put forward by E.A. Klimov:

1. There are personal qualities that are practically not cultivated, which are important for the success of activity.
2. There are different ways of adapting to the conditions of professional activity, which are the same in terms of labor productivity.
3. There are wide possibilities for eliminating the weak expression of individual abilities by training or using other abilities or methods of work.
4. It is necessary to form abilities taking into account the individuality of the person, to develop internal conditions taking into account external conditions.

The formation of professional culture of students, their correct orientation in general is an important process, in which it is very important to give advice based on professional activity. Professional culture in students should include human strength and potential, which are implemented in activities such as knowledge, qualifications, skills, abilities, moral and aesthetic development, worldview, methods and forms of communication with people, and the level of development of talent. This is a difficult task that requires serious preparation. Qualified actions based on the knowledge and experience of the student or things created from the products of labor activity, a social phenomenon that can arouse pleasure in others. Diagnostic and advisory work on career guidance, which is currently carried out by each educational institution among students, is a vivid example of this. As we have seen above, choosing a profession is a complex and long process. The problem is not only in the overall duration, but also in the sequence of stages. There are two dangers here. The first of them is that students postpone the process of career guidance due to the lack of clear and stable interests. This postponement is accompanied by general immaturity, infantilism of behavior. This situation becomes understandable if we recall that the process of career guidance is one of the main components of a mature and stable image of the "I", self-esteem.

Another factor that negatively affects the general culture established by society, which should be present in the professional activities of students, is professional deformation. Professional deformation is a change in a person's behavior and values under the influence of the professional community, working conditions and work experience. Professional deformation often develops in representatives of professions that require constant contact with other people: teachers, psychologists, doctors and medical workers, lawyers, investigators, prosecutors, managers of various levels and civil servants, etc. Also, professional deformation develops under the influence of a set of individual circumstances at a particular workplace. For example, doctors in the emergency department become callous and lose empathy: due to the lack of time for full communication with patients, a large volume of work, a chaotic environment, negative attitudes towards certain groups of patients, for example, people addicted to alcohol, communication with family members of the patient who interferes with work. In such cases, pedagogical correction of students is very important. By giving the following recommendations, we can look for solutions to the problems. 1. Identify the specific manifestations of professional deformation that bother you. It involves controlling your behavior so that you do not follow the usual behavior. 2. Learn to switch off from work.

To do this, you need to draw a line between your personal and professional life. You need to get enough rest for emotional and physical recovery. 3. Learn empathy. Sometimes try to look at the world from the perspective of your colleagues, clients and relatives. 4. Expand your horizons. To develop flexible thinking, educate yourself, find a new hobby and learn skills that are not related to work. 5. Contact a qualified teacher or psychologist. A specialist will help you identify negative patterns and explain how to change behavior and thinking.

In order to actively and purposefully influence the process of formation and development of professional orientation in students, we recommend the following:

Firstly, in order to help each student form a stable professional orientation during the educational process in a higher educational institution, it is necessary to take into account a set of pedagogical phenomena that ensure the success of education. Secondly, it is necessary to implement an individual approach to each student during higher education, to make wider use of the opportunities of professional orientation. Thirdly, taking into account the fact that a significant part of students choose a profession without understanding it by chance, it is possible to recommend a system of measures aimed at forming a professional vision of the world in students during the educational process in a higher educational institution.

Fourth, since most students are interested in current issues, and the use of scientific, problematic, deep knowledge, and instructional and technical tools in teaching is emphasized as a positive aspect in teaching specialized subjects, we recommend that teachers make lessons lively and interesting, based on new pedagogical technologies. Fifth, in order to form a professional orientation in students, we recommend introducing them to the professional profession and psychogram, and developing important professional qualities in pedagogical lessons, practical exercises, and educational hours with the help of group tutors.

Conclusion. You can ask people who know you well - family members, teachers, educators and psychologists, and friends - about the general norms and culture of your chosen profession, the media will help you learn more about the culture of the profession, special sources (literature, online platforms) will provide information about popular areas and their cultural norms, and based on your desires and goals in life, you can choose a profession that suits you best. Go out, analyze the information you have collected in depth, try to answer the question "what do I need in life?" If possible, it is advisable to consult with a qualified specialist in professional culture.

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